

Introducing the VISQAM Dataset: Toward Automated Map Interpretation

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Abstract

We introduce VISQAM, an open dataset designed specifically for visual question-answering (VQA) on thematic geographic maps. Comprising 1200 annotated images and 4594 QA pairs from four permissive-license sources, VISQAM enables the development of models capable of interpreting and understanding the complex spatial and thematic information encoded in maps. We fine-tuned Qwen3-VL-2B-Instruct on this dataset, achieving substantial performance improvements: BERTScore-F1 increased from 0.43 (base model) to 0.72 (fine-tuned), with exact match rising from 0.0 to 0.24. Our experiments highlight the challenges of spatial and relational reasoning in map interpretation. The fine-tuned model performs best on object-related questions, while relation questions prove most difficult, indicating the need for more examples of this question type in future expansions of the dataset. As automated map interpretation can improve access to spatial information, e.g. for visually impaired users, and facilitate knowledge extraction from cartographic products, VISQAM lays the groundwork for developing more advanced VQA systems.

Keywords: vqa, question-answering, cartography, chart understanding, geovisualization

1. Introduction

Geographic maps are fundamental to the Geosciences, serving as tools for visualizing data, communicating research findings, and describing spatial phenomena. However, interpreting maps requires sophisticated reasoning, as readers must process multiple visual variables simultaneously to extract information. Recent advances in computer vision have made visual question-answering (VQA) possible, allowing machines to comprehend image content and respond to questions in natural language. The complexity of charts and diagrams within VQA has motivated the development of dedicated datasets such as ChartQA (Masry et al. 2022) and models tailored for structured visual reasoning (Masry et al. 2023; Liu et al. 2023).

These systems have demonstrated value in terms of accessibility by enabling visually impaired users to access graphical content (Singh et al. 2023). In the geographical context, specialized VQA

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frameworks and assistive platforms have been developed to support blind and low vision users in spatial cognition (Hao et al. 2024), navigation (Morales et al. 2025), and map exploration (Li et al. 2025). By allowing users to interact with visualizations using natural language, these systems lower language barriers and make complex information more approachable for both the general public and experts.

While geographic VQA is gaining traction through datasets using satellite imagery (Wang et al. 2023; Shu et al. 2025), synthetic maps (Chang et al. 2022; Srivastava et al. 2025), or uniform cartographic styles (Chang et al. 2022; Ung et al. 2025), these efforts do not capture the diversity of cartographic products found in the Geosciences. Existing datasets that source geovisualizations from real-world scenarios tend to focus on specific types of questions. For example, FRIEDA (Pyo et al. 2026) focuses on spatial relations. Others lack an explicit geographic dimension in their questions (Koukouraki, Degbelo, and Kray 2025). We address this gap with VISQAM: an open dataset designed for VQA on diverse thematic maps drawn from real-life sources. VISQAM features diverse QA annotations spanning questions related to symbology, cardinal directions, thematic attributes, and object identification. We accompany this dataset with a baseline model that demonstrates the feasibility and challenges of this task.

2. Data and Methods

2.1. Map Sources

Our dataset comprises thematic maps from four primary sources, all released under permissive licenses to allow for open accessibility. First, we include Land Use/Land Cover (LULC) maps from *Copernicus Land Urban Atlas* covering European metropolitan regions (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service 2020). These maps were converted from PDF to PNG format and downscaled to 30% of their original dimensions to reduce the heterogeneity of file sizes within the dataset. Second, we source maps from the *Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service*¹ and the *European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts*², providing meteorological and atmospheric data visualizations at continent level. Third, we include choropleth maps from *Our World in Data* with world- and continent-wide coverage, specifically from the Energy & Environment³ theme ("Climate Change" and "Energy" subcategories). Finally, to improve generalizability across different map layouts, we cherry-picked thematic maps from the *Ubimap-L* dataset (J. Yang et al. 2025) and from papers published in the Copernicus Journals *Biogeosciences*⁴ and *Earth System Science Data*⁵, making sure that the map text is in English and the image resolution allows legibility. All images were converted to PNG format. The current release contains 300 annotated images from each source, with plans for expansion in the foreseeable future. Figure 1 shows representative sample images from the four main sources.

2.2. Map Annotations

For QA annotation, we developed a question bank of templates following GQA’s classification system, which categorizes questions according to their structural and semantic types (Hudson and Manning 2019). The structural type refers to the underlying syntactical structure of the question, which determines how it can be answered. These types include verify, query, choose, logical, and

Figure 1: Representative samples of map images comprising the VISQAM dataset. Images in categories (A), (C), and (D) are licensed under CC BY 4.0. Images in category (B) are licensed under Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 1159/2013. Full attribution details for all images are provided in the dataset annotations file.

compare. The semantic type refers to the main subject of the question.

We adapted the GQA semantic types for a geographic context case as follows: 1) object: for existence questions about geographic entities (e.g., "Is there a river in this region?"), 2) attribute: consider the location of a geographic feature (e.g., elevation, population density, coordinates), 3) category: related to feature classification within a geographic typology (e.g., LULC), 4) relation: for questions asking about spatial relationships between features, and 5) global: questions about overall characteristics of the mapped area such as map topic and geographic coverage.

The question bank includes templates with different combinations of structural and semantic types. The template questions were then randomly assigned to map images. Data curators manually adapted the templates to fit the specific content of each map and paired them with ground-truth answers. Each map image in the dataset was annotated with three to five QA pairs. Figure 2

illustrates an example of an image with two QA annotations: one of types *query-attribute* and one of types *verify-global*. The dataset contains 4594 QA pairs in total. Additionally, we annotated legend bounding boxes for every map. All annotations (QA pairs, legend bounding boxes) are provided in a COCO-like format (Lin et al. 2015) to facilitate interoperability.

question: "Which color represents 0-4 degrees Celsius of temperature?"

answer: "The green shade with the hexadecimal code #d9ff00."

structural: *query*, semantic: *attribute*

question: "Is the overall trend of temperature increasing across the map?"

answer: "Yes, it is increasing from the south and the north poles towards the equator."

structural: *verify*, semantic: *global*

Figure 2: Example of a map image sourced from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), licensed under CC BY 4.0 and ECMWF Terms of Use. On the right, two example QA annotations, of *query-attribute* and *verify-global* types.

2.3. Baseline Model

To demonstrate the dataset’s utility and establish a performance baseline, we fine-tuned Qwen3-VL-2B-Instruct, the most lightweight model from the Qwen3-VL family (A. Yang et al. 2025). We selected this architecture because its larger flagship model (Qwen3-VL-235B-A22-Instruct) ranks as the top-performing openly licensed model on the LMArena Vision Leaderboard⁶ as of December 2025, specifically under the permissive Apache 2.0 license. Given the computational demands of fine-tuning the larger model, we opted for the dense 2B variant as an initial test of the dataset’s potential. To reduce the computational cost, we employed LoRA for the fine-tuning. We split the dataset into 95% training (1140 samples) and 5% validation (60 samples) sets, keeping a balanced representation of all four map sources in each subset, and used LoRA for the fine-tuning on our university’s high-performance cluster PALMA II.

3. Evaluation

We evaluated the model performance on the validation split using the normalized exact match (EM) and the BERTScore-F1 metrics. In our implementation of EM, predictions score as correct only when the string matches exactly the reference text after normalization steps such as lowercasing, punctuation and whitespace removal. BERTScore measures semantic similarity between two strings by encoding their tokens into contextual BERT embeddings and computing pairwise cosine similarities (Zhang et al. 2020). Precision and recall are derived from the maximum token-level similarities between the prediction and the reference text. We report the BERTScore-F1

metric, which balances precision and recall by taking the harmonic mean of the two. These metrics were chosen for their complementarity: EM provides a strict measure of answer accuracy, while BERTScore-F1 accounts for semantic equivalence between predictions and expected answers. Evaluating the model using llm-as-judge, employed by Pyo et al. 2026, was considered but eventually not adopted, as it did not yield reliable results.

A comparison of the base Qwen3-VL-2B-Instruct model and the VISQAM fine-tuned version reveals substantial improvements. The base model achieved EM of 0.0 and a BERTScore-F1 of 0.43, whereas the fine-tuned model achieved EM of 0.24 and a BERTScore-F1 of 0.72. Table 1 shows the EM and BERTScore-F1 across the different question types. For structural types, compare questions show the greatest improvement and the highest score in both metrics post fine-tuning. For semantic types, object-related questions achieve the highest performance, whereas relation questions show the poorest results post fine-tuning. This pattern suggests that identifying and describing map elements is more achievable than reasoning about spatial or thematic relationships between them, highlighting key challenges in automating map interpretation.

Table 1: Exact Match (EM) and BERTScore-F1 by Question Type

Question Type	<i>Qwen3-VL-2B-Instruct</i>		<i>VISQAM-fine-tuned</i>	
	EM	BERTScore-F1	EM	BERTScore-F1
<i>Structural</i>				
Logical	0.00	0.48	0.20	0.71
Compare	0.00	0.28	0.52	0.84
Verify	0.00	0.35	0.40	0.73
Choose	0.00	0.39	0.17	0.70
Query	0.00	0.53	0.08	0.69
<i>Semantic</i>				
Attribute	0.00	0.37	0.26	0.72
Category	0.00	0.41	0.25	0.71
Global	0.00	0.49	0.24	0.74
Object	0.00	0.47	0.27	0.77
Relation	0.00	0.39	0.05	0.52
Overall	0.00	0.43	0.24	0.72

The VISQAM-fine-tuned model (v1.1.0) was additionally tested on topographic maps using a small set of map images sourced from the internet. The model performed well with this input type (images and questions of topographic interest); however, this serves as a qualitative sanity check rather than a rigorous evaluation, as no metrics were computed. The corresponding Kaggle notebook is available at <https://www.kaggle.com/code/ajayuchana/test-on-topomaps>.

4. Summary and Outlook

Our work addresses a critical gap in VQA research by providing an open dataset with diverse thematic geographic maps. By establishing baseline performance and identifying key challenges in spatial and relational reasoning, we demonstrate both the feasibility and the complexity of automated map interpretation. Future work includes expanding the dataset with additional annotated

images and developing architectures that explicitly make use of the legend bounding boxes to ground responses in map symbology. However, making the QA annotation process scalable remains a concern. A promising solution is to use the fine-tuned model itself as a pseudo-annotator for new map images, while retaining human verification of low-confidence predictions.

As the dataset grows, we will update the baseline results with retrained models to track performance improvements at scale. As map-based communication remains fundamental to the Geosciences, advancing the automated interpretation of cartographic products can make geospatial visualizations more accessible and easier to interact with.

Data and Software Availability

The dataset and baseline model are publicly available at <https://huggingface.co/datasets/koukeft/visqam/tree/1.2.0> and <https://huggingface.co/koukeft/qwen3v1-2B-instruct-visqam-finetuned/tree/v1.2.0> respectively. Instructions on how to use them and reproduce our evaluation results can be found at git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4earth/pilotsincubatorlab/incubator/visual-question-answering-for-thematic-maps.

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Notes

¹<https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu/charts/packages/cams/>

²<https://charts.ecmwf.int/>

³<https://ourworldindata.org/search?topics=Energy%20and%20Environment>

⁴<https://bg.copernicus.org/>

⁵<https://essd.copernicus.org/>

⁶<https://arena.ai/leaderboard/vision>

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